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On the microfoundations of technology transfer: Remarks from a Brazilian university¹

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Introduction

Innovation and economic growth have come to benefit considerably from knowledge transfer between the industry and universities (Guerrero et al., 2016). Active engagement of scientists with intellectual property (IP) commercialization is critical for success, especially for public universities in developing economies, which play a pivotal role in strengthening innovation capabilities in industrial agents (Fischer et al., 2019). In this ongoing research we dedicate attention to advance our understanding about the micro foundations of university-industry interactions regarding the production and commercialization of academic inventions, i.e., the complex individual-level aspects that are involved with the formation of an entrepreneurial orientation in academics (Hayter et al., 2021).

Objective and Method

Within the context of universities in emerging economies, this research seeks an in-depth knowledge of how processes of IP creation and commercialization unfold from the perspective of academics. Our objective is to relate these processes to certain factors such as field and type of research carried out in the university and patterns of interaction with industry. To this end, we are conducting interviews with inventors from the University of Campinas (Unicamp) – Brazil – in order to explore cases of IP commercialization spanning several fields of research and individual trajectories. Unicamp is one of the largest universities in Brazil, answering for over 6% of the country’s total scholarly output – according to SciVal. It is a public organization and one of the leading patenting institutions in the country.

So far, we’ve produced data from 14 interviews (Table 1). Individuals were selected from a list of IP commercialization cases made available by the university’s Technology Transfer Office (TTO).

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Table 1. Sample aspect

Interviewee #	Field of research	Year of PhD	Patent	Software	PPVP*
I-6	Agronomics	2011	0	0	6
I-12	Biology	1994	11	0	0
I-2	Chemistry	1984	16	0	0
I-7		1995	3	0	0
I-8		1995	18	3	0
I-1	Chemistry/Food Engineering	2006	4	0	0
I-13		1999	18	1	0
I-11	Computer Sciences	1987	6	3	0
I-4	Electric Engineering	2003	10	1	0
I-5		2006	1	0	0
I-9		1991	4	0	0
I-10		2005	8	2	0
I-14	Pharmacy	2004	12	0	0
I-3	Telecom. Engineering	2010	7	2	0

*plant and plant variety protection.

The first 14 interviews followed a structured protocol comprised of 6 inductive questions (Table 2), each followed by specific sub-questions to be addressed as needed.

Table 2. Interview protocol – lead questions

I.	How would you define yourself professionally?
II.	Could you tell us the story behind your first patent?
III.	Has your patent been commercialized in any way? How did this process take place?
IV.	Was the IP born out of a market/industry opportunities you recognized or out of research?
V.	How has your engagement with developing new technologies with market potential changed your research and teaching activities?
VI.	How do you evaluate the role of the university in the process of creating and commercializing your patent(s)?

Preliminary Results and Discussion

Interactions with Industry

The profile of industry interaction among Unicamp's inventors varies across the different fields in our sample. Academics from the Engineering field mentioned keeping a close contact with market partners. This leads to the creation of new research projects and targeted IP production. However, the extent to which such linkages are triggered by market demands seems to vary across specific sub-fields. While in some cases companies seek researchers to co-produce knowledge, the majority of interviewees report a typical technology transfer process in which IP is generated and then pushed to commercialization. Illustratively, one interviewee mentions that in his field of research, "naturally focused on application" (I-7), it is common to develop IP without a specific demand in mind. On two instances researchers claimed to develop an invention based on the observation of a specific sector's regulatory environment (I-2 and I-8). In both cases, the IP was developed first and prospective licensors were approached later. Beyond scientific particularities, such timing of approximation with

industrial partners emerged as an outcome of academics' proclivity towards being involved in networks comprehending agents outside of the university.

Commercialization

The majority of interviews underscored marginal success in IP commercialization. Although cases were sampled from the TTOs listing of commercialization activities, negotiations with an industrial partner were either inconclusive or did not render a marketable product. Reasons for this include:

- *Incompatibility with the industrial partner:* In some instances, objectives and expectation misalignments impacted the decision to not move forward with negotiations. For a specific case (I-10), the company wanted to apply the technology as soon as possible and asked for complete transfer of ownership over the IP with no financial compensation, only the promise of access to facilities for development and testing. The technology, however, was still in early stages of development and had yet to become application worthy. Another concern in this respect is timing issues of both scientific undertakings and negotiation processes with the university. This emerged as a particularly sensitive issue when projects involved co-creation of knowledge with companies.
- *Lack of funding:* For some researchers, IP commercialization or co-development with an industrial partner is a means to accrue funding for research projects. Therefore, the inventor himself does not necessarily seek out IP commercialization as a source of income, but as a way of assuring the continuation of research. In this case, technology transfer itself is not a legitimate goal for the researcher, a situation that created barriers for the translation of scientific results into technologies with minimum market viability.
- *Heavy reliance on the TTO:* All interviewees attribute a fundamental role to the TTO as a connector between them and industrial partners. By concentrating several time and resource consuming activities, such as patent filing, prospecting and negotiating with potential investors, the TTO leaves room for researchers to focus on their core activities. However, the majority does not rigorously follow up on the TTO and the negotiation of their IP, usually waiting to be contacted on occasion. By doing so, many researchers are unaware of the exact outcomes of commercialization. Such conditions indicate a feeble entrepreneurial identity in most analyzed cases. Only in one occasion (I-13) the researcher took an active role in the commercialization process.

Blockbuster patents

Our sample included one blockbuster patent, applied to the food industry, responsible for the university's most profitable commercial licensing currently active (I-13). In this specific case, we found that the university-industry interaction occurs at a much deeper level for a number of reasons. First, the technology meets a pressing demand from the industry. Second, the inventor sees his research as part of a cycle that "must end with application" (I-13), highlighting an entrepreneurial identity that perceives scientific knowledge as a means to generate economic and societal impact. Third, and as a result of these identity traits, is actively involved in seeking new opportunities to improve his solutions, participating on both academic and industry conferences in order to "be aware of what is out there" (I-13). Fourth, although the TTO is engaged in negotiating the technology, the researcher is personally involved with the industrial partner. To illustrate, he mentions that, although his invention did

not fit standard industrial quality tests, his team provided training for the industrial partner, perfecting the implementation of the technology to allow its commercial application.

Preliminary Remarks

The dynamics of IP production and commercialization, as well as the level of university-industry interaction, varies across fields of research and personal characteristics. Researchers from Engineering keep close contact with industrial partners, since companies usually come to these professionals, leading to targeted solutions. Other areas, such as Chemistry, Biology and Agronomics are less frequently sought out but have their own means of producing IP. However, inventions are not necessarily tailored to one specific industry.

The blockbuster case allowed us to identify key personal characteristics influencing the university-industry interaction. I-13 is a self-declared academic entrepreneur. He is actively engaged with industry and constantly seeks new opportunities for generating new technologies. His approach to research is problem-driven with application as the final goal. Given this close proximity to the industrial partner, trust between parties, as well as the chances for a successful IP commercialization, are increased. Following these examinations, we provide some initial insights on the micro foundations of technology transfer processes, highlighting not only the relevance of knowledge domains, but also the key role played by individual-level motivations and identity issues.

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